

PRAFULLA CHANDRA RAY MEMORIAL LECTURE*

BY DR. J. C. GHOSH

I am extremely grateful to the Indian Chemical Society for their invitation to deliver the Prafulla Chandra Ray Memorial Lecture this year.

We are meeting today under circumstances which are tragic beyond description. Prafulla Chandra's life was spent in the service of his country—even in serving his favourite science of chemistry, he maintained, he had no other object in life. It was not given unto him to see the dawn of freedom in his country. In some parts of India, that dawn, however, has not ushered in a bright day of hope but threatens to fade into darkness again. Calcutta is the heart of this area. Millions of men have been uprooted from their homes, and the soil which they held as dear as their lives. Many through the streets of Calcutta—helpless refugees without work; they live in squalor which has to be seen before it can be imagined; many live on doles which just keep the body and soul together. Respectable citizens transformed overnight into homeless wanderers, think of themselves as victims of Fate,—have no will left in them to resist its vagaries. Most of this terribly suffering humanity, however, are cursing the Indian leaders for having agreed to the partition, and are not in a mood to accept with philosophic resignation their present lot.

The thought that comes uppermost to my mind today is "Thy country, Prafulla Chandra, hath need of thee at this crisis in her history". It was at such hours of peril that his abilities shone forth at their best. He never believed in specialisation which kept the spirit bounded and poor. Time and again we have found the scientist laying aside his test tube and leading great movement for the relief of the distressed and preaching new ideas for the moral and material progress of his countrymen, based on self-help. He was never so moved as when he found men driven to sub-human levels of existence due to natural calamities or to forces beyond their control. On such occasions that frail little man could draw as it were, from hidden reserves within himself, superhuman stores of energy, and endow his co-workers with the confidence that where the spirit is willing, the flesh can never be too weak.

I recall vividly even today, how 37 years ago, the student community of Calcutta organised under his leadership relief operations for the sufferers of the Damodar flood of 1913. The embankments on the left side were breached on that occasion at several places and the whole tract now lying to the west of the Calcutta Burdwan chord line was devastated. All the mud houses collapsed, cattle died in thousands and the rice crop was destroyed. The condition of people on the right of the Damodar was much worse: it took days before communication with that area could be restored. I remember well how sons of rich families of Calcutta would come forward as volunteers under the

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inspiring influence of Dr. Ray, select, as their grotty leader, a youngster like Meghnad Saha who knew the ways of life in water logged areas, and carry loads of rice, cloth, salt and medicine to unknown villages wading waist-deep through mud and water. To them such education from the book of life was far more important than what was imparted to them in college classes. Sympathy for the village folk, their useful toil, and homely joys widened the outlook of the city bred youth, while the villager rejoiced in the conviction, that he was remembered when evil days befell him.

Prafulla Chandra was never tired of stating that it is on such strong foundations of understanding, sympathy and devoted service between different groups of men that a true nationhood is built up. It did not require any effort on his part to make himself at home among common people. Living a life of severe asceticism, and spending whatever he had for the benefit of the poor and the oppressed, he naturally gained the unbounded confidence of his countrymen. He was intensely human, and felt a peculiar delight if common people were to mistake him as one of themselves. As a young professor he used to come to College dressed in the cheapest buttoned up coat and trousers that the Chandny Chowk in Calcutta could supply. That dress was familiar to staff and students of Calcutta colleges; but of course not to the passengers at the Sealdah station. And it once happened that he was going to Darjeeling on medical advice to shake off malarial fever and was reclining against his luggages at the platform, waiting for a friend who had gone to the counter to purchase a second class ticket. A chaprasi of a European passenger accosted him by saying "Hallo, you are also waiting for your master as I am doing". "Where does your master stay in Darjeeling" and so on. Prafulla Chandra was answering these questions as best as he could without revealing his identity, when somewhat to the discomfiture of the chaprasi, the European passenger came and happening to recognise him, shook him by the hands.

They say that truth lived is a thousand time more potent than truth spoken. Words acquire a new meaning depending upon the person who speaks them. Likewise, thoughts acquire a new significance depending upon the person who expresses them. A word of hope and sympathy from Prafulla Chandra put more strength and courage in suffering humanity than all the good wishes of bureaucrats and intellectuals. An appeal from him for help would evoke response from the remotest corner of the country. Even a stony heart softens by touch with another which melts at sight of distress. And so when the great flood of 1922 overwhelmed North Bengal, and created unprecedented havoc, people rushed to him and acclaimed him as the leader for organising relief. How well he did this work has been thus narrated by a special representative of the Manchester Guardian :—

"There was a heavy rainfall from the 25th to 27th September, and the water rose to an unprecedented height. Throughout 700 sq. miles of a thickly populated countryside, more than half the houses collapsed, 12,000 heads of cattle perished, all fodder was ruined and the main crop was utterly destroyed. Government seemed to have no conception of the gravity of the situation. They were slow to move, the action taken was inadequate and what they gave was given ungraciously.

"In these circumstances a professor of chemistry, Sir P. C. Ray, stepped forward and called upon his countrymen to make good the Government's omissions. His call was answered with enthusiasm. The public of Bengal in one month contributed three lakhs of rupees; rich women giving their silks and ornaments, and the poor giving their spare garments. Hundreds of youngmen volunteered to go down and carry out the distribution of relief to the villagers, a task which involved a considerable amount of hard work and bodily discomfort in a malarious country.

"What greatly aggravated the public's dissatisfaction with Government's attitude was the fact that the disaster is generally attributed to the faulty design of the railways which is believed to make very inadequate provision for the passage of flood water. There is much evidence to support this view, but it was only after a lapse of a month and a half that Government promised an enquiry into the question.

"The enthusiasm of the response to Sir P. C. Ray's appeal was due partly to the Bengali's natural desire to score off the foreign Government, partly to genuine public sympathy with the sufferers, and very largely to Sir P. C. Ray's remarkable personality and position. Sir P. C. Ray is a scientist of world-wide repute. I do not think he can be said to be an orthodox Non-Co-operator, but he is a very strong Nationalist, and a very strong critic of Government. He is also a real organiser and a real teacher. I heard a European saying, 'If Mr. Gandhi had only been able to create two more Sir P. C. Rays he would have succeeded in getting Swaraj within this year'. A Bengali student told me, 'If any Government officer or any of the non-co-operating politicians had called for subscriptions the public would not have given even three farthings. But when Sir P. C. Ray calls everyone knows that the money will be spent and well spent, and not wasted.' I had the good fortune to see Sir P. C. Ray in Calcutta at his College of Science and I think I can understand why his fellow-countrymen feel so much confidence in him. One day he was gloating over vast and disorderly-looking stores of clothes, old and new, brought by Bengali sympathisers to his laboratories. The volunteers were busy under his eyes, bringing order out of disorder, and arranging for the despatch of the clothes to the scene of the relief operations. The next day I caught a glimpse of him assisting two young students to carry out some experiment in chemistry, and it seemed to me there was affection between the teacher and the taught. When I heard him talking about the Government I felt that I would sooner serve under him than be criticised by him. He is too warm-blooded and energetic a man to make a perfectly fair critic. But any man who feels aggrieved by his criticism has at least the satisfaction of knowing that unlike so many critics, Sir P. C. Ray would never shirk taking on the job himself if the chances were offered him, and that if he did take on the job he would be likely to put it through about as well and perhaps a little better than everybody else.

"My enquiries on the spot made it quite clear that Government have lost immensely in prestige over the whole affair, and that Non-Co-operation has won what Government have lost, thanks to the fine work of Sir P. C. Ray's volunteers."

Prafulla Chandra was like a gem with many facets radiating light in many directions. I have naturally taken as my first theme that facet which gives us a vision of democratic life in the Union of India, where each member of the Society palpitates

with true humanitarian feeling, when another elsewhere is adversely affected ; where the diverse elements in our cultural and economic life are cemented together, as in a mosaic, by forces of love and good will.

To Fellows of the Indian Chemical Society, Prafulla Chandra's work as a Scientist is generally known. It is time, however, that some of his old students prepare a complete review of his researches, and interpret some of his experimental results in the light of newer ideas. As a boy he was passionately fond of studies in history and literature ; while at Albert School, he came under the influence of the Rector, Krishna Behary Sen who was also the editor of the Indian Mirror which the young student read with eagerness every morning before the classes began. He resolved that when he grew up, he would wield as facile a pen as Krishna Behary. Being of studious habits, he read whatever books were there in his father's library. Even Johnson's Dictionary in two quarto volumes caught his fancy, and he committed to memory hundreds of apt quotations from classical authors. One such quotation he would often repeat in later life to his students "Ignorance is the curse of God, Knowledge the wing wherewith we fly to Heaven." In the Tatwa Bodhini Patrika, the organ of the Brahma Samaj, he read with the greatest appreciation, the writings and sermons of Debendranath Tagore, Keshab Chandra Sen, Rajnarain Basu ; and from these it was but another step to come to Raja Ram Mohan Ray. A window in his mind was opened, as it were, by the famous letter of Ram Mohan Ray to Lord Amherst in 1822 advocating "the promotion of a more liberal and enlightened system of instruction including mathematics, natural philosophy, chemistry, anatomy and other useful sciences, which may be accomplished by employing a few gentlemen of talent and learning, educated in Europe and providing a College furnished with necessary books, instruments and other apparatus". Even half a century later, this hope of Ram Mohan that modern science should dominate the education of Indian youth had remained an empty dream. Franklin's biography he read over and over again, and there he was struck by the observation, so allied to that of Ram Mohan that the most certain method of human betterment was improvement in natural knowledge. The die was cast. Shakespeare and Madhusudan, Gibbon and Rajendra Lal Mitra must take back seats in the garden of his mind. He would devote himself to the study of modern sciences.

Prafulla Chandra was born with a silver spoon in his mouth. But even before he completed his school education the family estates dwindled into insignificance due to the debts incurred by his father ; there was therefore no hope that he could be given any help from home for scientific studies in Europe. To this handicap was added the more serious one of a fragile constitution. At the age of 13 his health was almost wrecked by an obstinate attack of dysentery, which impaired his digestive organs and arrested his natural growth during adolescence. He had to discontinue his studies in school for more than 2½ years and to submit himself, ever after, to a strict dietary discipline. But these handicaps only spurred young Prafulla to greater efforts. While reading for his degree with physics and chemistry as his optional subjects, he was secretly preparing for the Gilchrist scholarship examination which required a fair acquaintance with Latin, Sanskrit and French. It was an All-India competition and his success in 1882 gave him the cherished opportunity for proceeding to Great Britain

for higher studies. He entered the University of Edinburgh in October, 1882, and his subjects of study were chemistry, physics, botany and zoology. In chemistry he came under Crum Brown, whom he learnt to esteem, and with fellow students like Hugh Marshall Alexander Smith, James Walker, the atmosphere was such that he became passionately fond of chemistry. His studies for the B.Sc. degree were interrupted for a time when he competed for a prize on the best essay on "India, before and after the mutiny". In this "he indulged in many bitter diatribes against the British Rule" and the essay was judged among those *Proxime accesserunt*. It did, however, one good thing—Ray discovered that he had the faculty of writing with facility, a faculty which he used with great power in later life.

The essay written, he worked hard in his favourite subject of chemistry and obtained the D.Sc. degree in 1888 on the basis of a thesis in inorganic chemistry. He was honoured in due course by the award of a special scholarship by the Gilchrist Foundation and of the Hope Prize Scholarship, and also by his election to the position of Vice-President of the Edinburgh University Chemical Society. The simple life and the cheap living of those days in a Scottish University made an abiding impression on him. Students left to fend for themselves at an early age and protected by poverty from vicious amusements—lived in an atmosphere of high endeavour, in which University education was of real value as a preparation for life.

He now tried to join the Indian Educational Service; but high honours at the University, strong testimonials from professors of repute and powerful recommendations from well-wishers like Sir W.M. Muir and Sir Charles Bernard were of no avail at the India Office in London.

He returned to Calcutta in 1888 and, after a year of waiting, obtained the post of an assistant professor at the Presidency College, Calcutta on Rs. 250 a month. Persons with inferior qualifications were holding high appointments as professors in the Indian Educational Service, and he naturally felt the injustice that had been done to him. But he was determined to make the best use of his opportunities. In Europe the reputation of a professor depends more on his capacity for extending the bounds of knowledge rather than that for actual teaching. But in India this tradition was sadly lacking. From the very beginning of his career Dr. Ray felt it to be his mission in life to bring this tradition of Europe into the atmosphere of Indian Universities and to create an enthusiasm for research in his young students.

His training in Edinburgh was primarily in the field of Inorganic Chemistry and his researches in the early days of professorship were mostly confined to this branch of knowledge. His contributions till 1896, when he discovered mercurous nitrite, were mostly of a routine type which gave indication of high skill in preparation and analysis. But from 1896 till 1920, he devoted himself to the study of nitrites. Of this work extending over a quarter of a century Prof. Armstrong remarked as follows:

The way in which you have gradually made yourself "master of nitrites" is very interesting and the fact that you have established that, as a class, they are far from the unstable bodies, chemists had supposed, is an important contribution to our knowledge.

He extended his researches later to the field of organic sulphur and organo-metallic compounds. Many of his colleagues did not like the foul smell that came out of his laboratory, but he himself seemed to be oblivious of it. With the discovery of Vitamin B, as a sulphur compound, the indifference to the handling of sulphur compounds has disappeared, but it was not so when Dr Ray worked in this field. He was not so much interested in the synthesis of these compounds as in the nature of the chemical reactions which resulted in their formation. Long chain sulphur compounds obtained by the reaction of dithioethylene glycol with ethylene bromide, excited him immensely, but modern theories of polymer formation were not there to guide him in these researches and carry forward the investigations to their logical conclusions.

I would, today, from more than two hundred papers bring to your notice a few that, in my opinion, may give you an idea of the scope and value of his work.

Mercurous nitrite (*J. Asiatic Soc.*, 1896), obtained as yellow thin crystals when dilute nitric acid containing 13 to 14% of N_2O_5 reacts with mercury in the cold. The *Nature* remarked that the Journal of the Asiatic Society can scarcely be said to have a place in Chemical Libraries, but this number contained a paper by Prof. Ray, on mercurous nitrite which is worthy of note.

Mercuric hyponitrite.—A neat method of preparation is by interaction of mercuric nitrite with potassium cyanide whereby cyanide is oxidised to cyanate and nitrite reduced to hyponitrite (*J. C. S.*, 1897).

Preparation in the pure state of the nitrites of alkaline earths (*J. C. S.*, 1905), magnesium nitrite being the least stable and forming a link between the nitrites of zinc and cadmium and those of calcium, strontium and barium.

Preparation of the double nitrites of mercury (ic) with alkali and alkaline earths. (*J. C. S.*, 1910).—The combining power of mercuric nitrite was found to increase as the atomic weight of the other metal decreased

Nitrites of the mercuri-alkyl or aryl ammonium series (*J. C. S.*, 1912).—The molar conductivity of mono-amine salts is similar to alkali metal nitrites, while ethylenediamine salts behave as alkaline earths nitrites. The complexes may be represented as $[R NH_2 \cdot HgNO_2] NO_2$ and $[C_2H_4(NH_2)_2 \cdot Hg] (NO_2)_2$.

Methyl ammonium nitrite, nitrites of the alkyl ammonium bases: Tetramethyl ammonium hyponitrite (*J. C. S.*, 1911).—Unlike mercuric nitrite which yields complex salts with alkyl or aryl amines, double decomposition of silver nitrite with alkyl amine hydrochlorides in cold aqueous solution gave nitrites of the alkyl ammonium series. Prof. Dey who was associated with Dr. Ray in these researches has given an illuminating account of this work from first hand knowledge in the last year's memorial lecture.

Decomposition and sublimation of ammonium nitrite: Vapour density of ammonium nitrite (*J. C. S.*, 1909, 1912).—In noticing these papers, *Nature* (Aug. 13, 1912) remarked that Prof. Ray has added to his success in preparing ammonium nitrite in a tangible form, a further accomplishment in determining the vapour density of this very fugitive compound. This paper on vapour density in which Dr. N. R. Dhar was his collaborator was read by Prof. Ray in a crowded meeting of the London Chemical Society at the end of which Sir William Ramsay and Dr. Veley paid a warm tribute to Dr. Ray and his pupils for their valuable researches on ammonium and amine nitrites.

Velocity of decomposition and the dissociation constant of nitrous acid (*J. C. S.*, 1917).—This paper is of peculiar interest to me (*J. C. Ghosh*) as I had the privilege of collaborating with *Dr. Ray* in this research. It was shown that a solution of nitrous acid can be obtained at 0°C by double decomposition, that it can be concentrated by freezing out the solvent water, that it decomposes with a monomolecular velocity constant, that its dissociation constant as a weak acid can be approximately estimated. It was also noticed, contrary to expectation, that nitrous acid as such reacted very slowly with urea—an observation which was utilised by *Werner* in postulating a new constitution of urea.

Mercaptans and Mercaptides

Dr. Ray's abiding interest in mercury nitrites led him to study reactions of mercuric nitrite with mercaptans (*J. C. S.*, 1916, 131, 603). The resulting nitromercaptides of the formulae $RSHgNO_2$ and $RSHg(NO_2)_2$ gave complex sulphonium compounds of the type $R_2S_2 \cdot HgI_2 \cdot R \cdot I$ which were represented by the formula

Crystals of the compound $I \cdot Hg \cdot S \cdot S \cdot Hg \cdot I$ exhibit remarkable phototropism. Potential mercaptans behaved similarly or formed complexes. For example, with 2:5-dithiol-1:3:4-thiodiazole gave a trinuclear condensation product $(C_2N_2S_3)_x Hg_3O$, where $x = 2, 3, 4$ or 6. These furnished on interaction with alkyl iodides long-chain sulphonium compounds (*J. C. S.*, 1919, 261, 541). Phenylmercaptan gave a mercaptide of the formula Ph_2S_3Hg , which yielded the sulphonium compound

α -Naphthyl mercaptan behaved similarly (*J. C. S.*, 1919, 1148).

The study of these complex sulphur compounds led him to investigate the formation and behaviour of some organic sulphides and mercaptans, actual and potential (*J. C. S.*, 1922, 323). It was shown that chloropicrin could be conveniently used as a reagent for the diagnosis of real and potential mercaptans. The latter invariably parted with some sulphur in the free condition when the reagent was added, but the former did not. Thiocarbamide and thioacetamide behaved like real mercaptans towards $HgCl_2$, $PtCl_4$ and $CuCl_2$ (*J. C. S.*, 1919, 871).

Interaction of ethylenedibromide and alcoholic KSH gave the compound $HS(C_2H_4S)_2$, C_2H_4SH and the corresponding tetrasulphide $(C_2H_4)_3S_4$ along with a trisulphide of the formula $(C_2H_4S)_3$ and more complex polysulphides (*J. C. S.*, 1920, 1090).

The oxidation of triethylene-tetra- and tetra-sulphides.—Triethylene-trisulphone was obtained with permanganate, and with nitric acid, a disulphone. Benzylidene-diethylene

tetrasulphide and benzyldiene-diethylene trisulphide were obtained by the interaction of dithioglycol and benzyldiene chloride, byproducts being diethylene disulphide and diethylene tetrasulphide (*J. C. S.*, 1923, 2174; 1925, 1141).

Trimethelene dibromide gave, besides the expected mercaptan, the corresponding disulphide (*J. I. C. S.*, 19-9, 865).

Dithioethylene glycol and ethylene bromide furnished a very interesting series of long-chain compounds of the type $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4)_x\text{Br}$ (*J. I. C. S.*, 1926, 75). In this way macromolecular sulphur compounds were obtained.

Studies on the tautomeric changes of chain compounds showed that thiocarbamide passes on to the thiol configuration in presence of monochloroacetic acid (*J. C. S.*, 1914, 2159; 1916, 698). Similar tautomeric changes were induced in thiocarbamide, thioacetamide and thiobenzamide by mercuric nitrate, mercuric chloride, cupric chloride, platinum chloride and iodine.

Some mercaptans of the purine group were synthesised for the first time (*J. C. S.*, 1923, 1957) and condensed heterocyclic systems were derived by the action of organic halides on 2:5-dithiol-1:3:4-thiodiazole (*J. C. S.*, 1919, 1308). Complex products were also obtained from 2-thiol-5-thiol 4-phenyl-4:5-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole and 2:5-dithiol-1:3:4-thiodiazole and organic halides (*J. I. C. S.*, 1926, 23).

Thioacetamide and monochloroacetic acid in acetone gave the interesting compound α : β -thiocrotonic acid (*J. C. S.*, 1917, 507)

Ethyl thioacetoacetate and ethyl thioacetone dicarboxylate were obtained from ethyl acetoacetate and acetone dicarboxylate by their interaction with H_2S and HCl in alcohol. S-Alkyl derivatives of ethyl thioacetoacetate $\text{CH}_3-\text{C}(\text{SR})=\text{CH}.\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$ was obtained from ethyl thioacetoacetate and alkyl iodide (*J. C. S.*, 1933, 75). Acid hydrolysis of these compounds yielded mercaptans and acetone whereas alcoholic potash furnished alkylated mercaptocrotonic acids.

Oxidation of triethylene tetrasulphide with nitric acid was found to produce ethylene disulphonic acid, but potassium permanganate gave the expected tetrasulphone which combined with metallic sulphates to form a new and interesting series of double salts (*J. C. S.*, 1924, 207). Hydrolysis of allyl thiocarbamide resulted in two isomeric allyl amines, b. p. 53-54° (HCl) and 57-58° (H_2SO_4) (*J. Asiatic Soc. Bengal*, 1912, 8, 371).

The most important contribution of Sir P. C. Ray on organo-metallic complexes are those which led him to postulate varying valencies for platinum, gold and iridium. These postulates have been proved by a series of careful experiments which involved the interaction of platinum, gold and iridium chlorides with organic sulphides and mercaptans. For example, with dithioethylene glycol platinum chloride forms the complex of the formula $\text{Pt}(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4\text{SH})_x$, where $x=3, 4, 5, 6$ or 8 , the platinum in these compounds functioning as ter-, quadri-, quinque-, hexa- or octa-valent according to experimental conditions.

Diethyl sulphide similarly produced a series of compounds, viz., (a) $\text{PtCl}.\text{Et}_2\text{S}$; (b) $\text{PtCl}_2.2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$; (c) $\text{PtCl}_3.2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$; (d) $\text{PtCl}_4.2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$; and (e) $\text{PtCl}_5.2\text{Et}_2\text{S}, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Of

these, the compound (b) has been isolated in six isomeric forms and constitution of three of them has been accounted for in the following way : (1) Blomstrand's *cis*-compounds, (2) Blomstrand's *trans*-compounds and (3) $[\text{Pt}(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_4]\text{PtCl}_4$. Compound (c) is regarded as a molecular compound of (b) and (d). This has been proved by separation of the two constituent molecules on crystallisation from alcohol and confirmed by the action of ammonia. Compound (e) shows a higher co-ordination value than six. Similar compounds have also been obtained from benzyl sulphide. Compound (b) and compound (d) are represented by the following co-ordination formulae :

The constitution of these complexes were also studied by interaction with organic bases and determining their ionisabilities.

With mercaptanic radicals gold, like platinum, forms compounds in which it behaves as a bi-, ter-, quadri- or quinque-valent atom (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 63; 1928, 5, 527; 1930, 7, 67). An example of bivalent gold is furnished by the crystalline compound $2\text{AuCl}_2 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S}_2$. With dithioethylene glycol, the compound $2\text{AuCl} \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S}_2)_2$ is obtained. This is regarded as a compound containing bi- and tervalent or quadrivalent gold. An example of quinquevalent gold is furnished by the compound, $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S}_2)_5\text{Au}_2$. That medium has a profound influence on the valency of gold is proved by the fact that, in acetone, dithioethylene glycol and gold chloride form the above compound, but a different compound, viz., $\text{Au}_3\text{Cl} \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S}_2)_3$ in which gold is tervalent is obtained in ethereal solution. A series of compounds where gold assumed different valency conditions was also obtained by treating gold with some other organic sulphides, particularly, 1,1-dithian.

From iridium chloride the following compounds were obtained (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 276; 1932, 251) : $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Me}_2\text{S}$, $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{S}$, $\text{Ir}_2\text{Cl}_5 \cdot 4\text{Me}_2\text{S}$, $\text{IrCl}_5 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (*cis*- and *trans*-isomer). Similar compounds were obtained from dibenzyl sulphide.

Other metallic complexes obtained are $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$, $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}_2$, $\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$ (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 711, 689).

His last contribution related to fluorination of organic compounds (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 93; 1936, 427). This was achieved by double decomposition of anhydrous thallus fluoride with reactive organic bromo-compounds. Ethyl and methyl fluoroformates, fluoroacetone, fluoroacetal etc. were thus obtained.

In recognition of these researches, Dr. Ray was elected in 1934, an Honorary Fellow of the Chemical Society of London. Sir Gowland Hopkins and Professor C. Matignon were the two other recipients of this honour on this occasion. This appreciation of his services by his fellow chemists of the Commonwealth touched him deeply.

Side by side with the pursuit of these researches, which he was carrying out in the laboratory, he was also indulging in his favourite hobby—researches into the History of Chemistry. But it was not long before he fell a victim to insomnia and for more than half a century he was unable to do any literary work at night, as every such effort kept

him awake for several nights in succession. "Early to bed and early to rise" became his motto and he spent religiously a couple of hours in the morning for serious study. Encouraged by the French Savant Berthelot, he instituted a vigorous search for Sanskrit manuscripts bearing upon Chemistry and Alchemy. The results of these studies was embodied in the "History of Hindu Chemistry" of which the first volume was published in 1902. This monumental labour of love was welcomed with high encomium both in India and outside as adding a very interesting chapter to the history of sciences and and of the human spirit. The Vice-Chancellor of the University of Durham in conferring on Dr. Ray the honorary degree of D.Sc. referred to this monumental work "of which both the scientific and linguistic attainments are equally remarkable, and of which, if of any book, we may pronounce that it is definitive." In this self-imposed task, Dr. Ray was guided by the hope that a rediscovery of the glories of the past might bring to his countrymen, confidence in a bright future.

To him, the foundation of the Indian Chemical Society was the realisation of a long cherished dream. It took tangible shape in 1920 when as a result of his fourth visit to England he realised that Indian contributions to the knowledge of chemistry were so rapidly expanding that the Journal of the Chemical Society, London, might find it difficult to arrange for their publication. It happened that Bhatnagar, Mukherjee and Ghosh were then working in the laboratories of Professor Donnan in London. They were fortunate in that they had each a small research room for their use; and Bhatnagar being a vegetarian, they often prepared simple lunch in Indian fashion in the laboratories. The "Chelas" gave a standing invitation to the "Guru" to partake of this simple midday fare, which he often did. In one of these luncheon meetings, the trio pledged themselves to the proposition that on return to India, they would spare no efforts to bring into being the Indian Chemical Society with Dr. Ray as the first President. Mukherjee willingly offered to take up the onerous task of the first Secretary of the Society. The Society was founded in 1924 with a journal of its own; and in reply to congratulations from the President and Council of the Chemical Society, London, Dr. Ray wrote as follows:—

"The J. C. S. has hitherto been the only organ of chemists throughout the British Empire, and the Publication Committee have been hard put to it to find space for the ever-increasing number of communications and have often been under the necessity of appealing to authors of papers to abridge them as far as possible. This will explain the necessity of founding the Indian Chemical Society, with an organ of its own.

More than 40 years ago, while a student at Edinburgh, I almost dreamt a dream that, God willing, a time would come when modern India would also be in a position to contribute her quota to the world's stock of scientific knowledge, and it has been my good fortune to see my dream materialise. I have shown in my History of Hindu Chemistry that this branch of science was zealously pursued in ancient India and I have now the satisfaction of finding chairs of Chemistry in most of the Universities of India filled by my own pupils, who have also been regular contributors to the J. C. S..... I can scarcely suppress the feelings which arise in me as I am penning these lines. Thanking you once more for your good wishes,

Yours etc.,
(Sd). P. C. RAY.

The last two lines of the letter quoted above could have been only written by a great teacher who would seek victory every where but would consider that day the proudest in his life, when his own student surpasses him in attainments—

सर्व्वं जयन्ति पुत्रान् शिष्यान् पराजयम् ।

In his autobiography he writes of his lecture work as follows :—

“Throughout my twenty-seven years career at the Presidency College, I made it a point to lecture mainly to the junior classes. Boys coming fresh from High Schools are very teachable as they represent so much clay in the potters hand to be moulded into the desirable shape. My lectures were never based upon any particular text-books. A good portion of the session—July, August and September—was taken up in finishing the three elements, namely oxygen, hydrogen and nitrogen, as also their compounds. I took good care to give my pupils an historical insight by weaving into my lectures—stories of the discovery of oxygen—the contributions of Priestley, Lavoisier, and Scheele and their rival claims. Under the oxides of nitrogen, again, the atomic theory, specially the law of definite and multiple proportions, was given prominence and Dalton was brought on the stage so to speak and a sort of living personal contact was sought to be established between ‘the makers of modern Chemistry’ and my pupils. In short, I took good care to have the groundwork on a solid foundation.”

He believed “that the business of the university was not the transformation of undergraduates into fountains of knowledge. Its business is the difficult task of teaching students how facts are converted into truth. A mind receptive to novelty, capable of wisdom, inclined to moderation—these are the excellences at which it aims. The university has failed when its students are not aroused to passionate discussion amongst themselves or awakened to the study of great books.” In his class room, topics were often discussed which had sometimes nothing to do with chemistry. Thus speaking of glass as impervious to water and non-conductor of heat, he would suggest that water inside such a glass tumbler handed over by a sweeper cannot be polluted and would proceed to drink that water and invite the students to do so ; or that bones of cattle when burnt become inorganic calcium phosphate and that such burnt bits of bones may be chewed by Hindus. Speaking of Cavendish he would say how the great scientist felt extremely nervous in the presence of ladies, and would add that he did not know how he would himself fare in a similar situation. He would also lament that sons of the well-to-do in India never indulge in hobbies which extend the bounds of knowledge. He would describe how the self-taught Davy isolated the alkali elements and proved the elementary nature of chlorine. He would then narrate the history of the Royal Institution—the epoch-making discoveries of the Professors there culminating in the work of Dewar who liquified hydrogen when he was working there on deputation from India as a guest professor. Or he would describe how Berzelius in a small private laboratory made epoch-making contributions with the help of one laboratory assistant who was also the maid of the house, and how, after reading Davy’s memoir he exclaimed “Hearst thou Anna, thou shalt not in future call chlorine, oxymuriatic acid”. Discussing how Cannizzaro resuscitated the famous hypothesis of Avogadro, he would describe how Cannizzaro once shut up his laboratory, and shouldered the musket, exclaiming that “science can wait, but fight for freedom cannot”.

There was rarely a student in the B. Sc. Honours classes in chemistry of the Presidency College who did not know Dr. Ray personally and had not confided in him his hopes and aspirations and even his personal joys and sorrows. The result was that most of the bright and adventurous students after taking their Honours degree, would prepare a thesis under his guidance in lieu of a part of the examination for the M.Sc. degree. This helped the rapid expansion of a school of chemistry, seeds of which were sown in the first decade when he started taking research students as collaborators.

He retired from the Presidency College in 1916, to join the University College of Science as the Palit Professor of Chemistry on the invitation of the maker of the modern University of Calcutta - Sir Asutosh Mookerjee. The farewell address quoted below moved him to tears :-

"Your place in the college, Sir, we are afraid, can never be filled. Men will come and men will go but where else can we possibly expect to find again that sweetness of disposition, that vigour of simplicity, that unwearied spirit of service, that broad-based culture, that wisdom in deliberation and debate which for the space of thirty years or more endeared you so much to your pupils?

Yours was, Sir, indeed no small achievement. Your way of life, with its distinct Indian traits, recalled us to the sweet and simple and manly days of Indian attainment. You have been to us all through a guide, philosopher and friend. Easy of access, ever-pleasant, ever-willing to help the poor and needy student with your counsel and your purse, living a life of sturdy, celibate simplicity, with genuine patriotism, not loud but deep, you have been to us an ancient Guru reborn, a light and an inspiration from the treasure-house of old Indian spirituality.

When the history of India's intellectual attainment in the modern era comes to be written, your name will be mentioned in the very vanguard of progress as the maker of modern chemistry in India. The credit and the glory of being the pioneer in the field of chemical research and of giving the impetus to scientific curiosity in this country is yours. Your 'History of Hindu Chemistry' has opened a new chapter of Indian attainment and built a bridge over the abyss of the past whereon our researchers may shake hands with the spirits of a Nagarjuna and a Charaka.

And you have effected more. The theoretical study of chemistry has impelled you to its application to the natural resources of the country and the Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works is a living testimony to what un-aided Indian Science and business organisation can accomplish.

In the evening of your life, Sir, when men seek for rest and repose, you have preferred to remain in harness, to make the torch of Science you lighted a generation ago, burn steady and clear! May the College of Science and the cause of chemical research profit long by your untiring zeal! May many more and yet many more groups of eager investigators be sped on this path with your blessing!"

In his reply he expressed the hope that the fire which had been kindled in the hearts of young men to extend the bounds of knowledge would be kept burning on from generation to generation of our students till it illuminated the whole of our motherland. If any one were to ask him what treasures he had piled up at the end of his career,

he would, like Cornelia of old, point to the bright young men who had joined him in the quest of the unknown in the frontiers of Science.

The hopes of Sir Asutosh that Government would come forward with generous contributions to supplement the princely endowments of Sir Tarak Nath Palit and Sir Rash Behary Ghosh, for building up the College of Science, were not fulfilled. The University was only permitted to spend Rs. 12,000 a year from the Imperial grant for the upkeep of the laboratories. Men in high places in Indian public life, were not wanting, who compared this paltry help with the generous assistance from public funds given to the Indian Institute of Science at Bangalore and the Royal Institute of Science at Bombay and drew the conclusion that the prejudice against Science College, Calcutta, arose from the condition of the Trust deeds that none but Indians should hold the Chairs. Dr Ray decided that the salary payable to him as Professor should be spent for the development of the Chemistry Department of the College. In 1936 he retired from active service and was appointed Emeritus Professor of Chemistry in the University of Calcutta. Of him, as a teacher of youth, as a Guru inspiring his disciples with high ideals and the spirit of conquest in the domain of knowledge, Rabindranath wrote as follows:-

“ It is stated in the Upanishads that the One said, ‘I shall be many’. The beginning of creation is a move towards self-immolation. Acharya Prafulla Chandra has become many in his students and has made his heart alive in the hearts of many. And that could not have been at all possible had he not unreservedly made a gift of himself. This power of creation having its inception in self-sacrifice is a divine power. The glory of this power in the Acharya will never be worn out by decrepitude. It will extend further in time through the ever-growing intelligence of youthful hearts; by steady perseverance they will win new treasures of knowledge.”

Great as he has been as a teacher, he has also proved a most successful man of action. He has been responsible for establishing many industrial enterprises, of which the creation of the Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works is the most remarkable. When, as a young D.Sc. of Edinburgh, he was trying to secure an appointment in the Education Department, the Director of Public Instruction told him once that if he was such a clever chemist why did he not start industries. The young professor felt that the cheap and innumerable raw materials of Bengal could be converted into costly finished products with the aid of the scientific knowledge that he commanded.

Unaided, and with a capital of a few hundred rupees saved from his small salary, he began the preparation of pharmaceuticals at his own home. His duties at college were exacting. His research work in the laboratory continued every day from 10-30 A.M. to 5 P.M., his health was much below normal, but the will to achieve success as an industrialist was unconquerable.

In a few years the house at 91, Upper Circular Road, except for the bed-room which he occupied, had the appearance of a factory. His pharmaceutical preparations soon secured well-merited recognition and the business rapidly expanded. In 1902 the Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works were converted into a limited concern with a capital of 2 lakhs of rupees, and Sir Prafulla made over his share in the concern to a trust created for conducting a High School and other beneficent activities in his

native district of Khulna. Today, the Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works is the biggest concern of its kind in India and with branch factories at Bombay and Kanpur, manufactures and sells goods worth one and half a crore of rupees every year.

Dr. Ray was a close associate of Sir M. Visveswaraya in the campaign-Industrialise or perish. Ever since his retirement from Government service he had given freely of his money, his time and his advice to all who were prepared to take reasonable risk in developing new industries and in his public speeches, he would give high praise to pioneers who from small beginnings had built up industries which gave gainful occupation to our countrymen and reduced the dependence of India on foreign countries for her essential needs.

A man of wide culture, interested in almost all activities of human life, he came to occupy in his later years, a unique position in the public life of the country. He travelled far and wide all over India ; there was no nook and corner of his home province of Bengal with which he was not familiar. As he himself expressed it, sooner or later he found himself "the property of anybody and everybody, and was called upon by various educational institutions, by conferences, by the periodical papers and by all those interested in the development of industrial and political life of India to address his countrymen on subjects which so closely affected their national welfare and and prosperity". He was a man of indomitable will. A life-long sufferer from dysentery and insomnia, he took these maladies very lightly. He would even tell us "if you wished to live a long and useful life, you should nurse an incurable disease," and he would give examples of scores of people who had done so. He regretted nothing more than time wasted. And so, we find, that in the evening of his life when others would have taken well-earned rest, he was moving about from place to place, day in and day out, exhorting his countrymen to be self-reliant, not to resign themselves to fate, but build up their future on their own efforts, reminding them that the key to the success of the western nations was their belief that they can make their own future. He appealed to the middle classes of Bengal to place enterprise ahead of security, to take to pursuits involving manual work and to banish from their minds the craving for salaried jobs. The story of such a life, as Professor Armstrong wrote, is not only fascinating ; it has an altogether special value as a presentation of a complex mentality unique in character, range of ability and experience—a life over-full of action, of unusually varied occupations and interests, of the highest endeavour, ever pulsating with vitality and intellectual force.

One often wonders—what is there beyond death? But Prafulla Chandra will not die. He will ever live in the hearts of his countrymen!

JAI HIND!